

INVESTIGATION OF THE SPECIFIC EFFECT OF A DENTAL GEL BASED ON THE HANDELIA PLANT

N. Temirova

Z.T. Fayziyeva

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent City, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: nargizazafarovna2501@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17342789>

Relevance. Due to the high prevalence of oral inflammatory diseases among the population of our republic, the development of natural-based dental gels and the study of their activity is considered relevant.

Objective: To study the biological activity of a dental gel obtained from the Handelia plant.

Materials and Methods. The anti-inflammatory effect of a gel containing the liquid extract of Handelia with pubescent leaves was studied using a rat gingivitis model. The experiment was conducted on white rats of both sexes, weighing 180–220 g. To induce the gingivitis model (experimental gingivitis), a 5% sodium hydroxide solution was applied to the gingival surface for 10 seconds. After 1 hour, the inflammatory process developed, accompanied by pronounced swelling of the gingival mucosa. For the following 7 days, the gingival surface was treated with the gel containing the liquid extract of Handelia with pubescent leaves and with Kamistad gel. The degree of manifestation of the inflammatory reaction was evaluated using a 0–4 point scale.

Experimental Results. Before the study, the condition of the oral cavity and gingival mucosa of the animals was recorded as pale pink in color, without visible pathological changes, moist, without bleeding, and with the gums closely attached to the teeth. After the application of 5% sodium hydroxide solution, gingival swelling developed, a pronounced erythema appeared, and subsequently ulceration was observed.

On the first day of the experiment, the degree of gingival inflammation ranged from 3.67 ± 0.21 to 3.83 ± 0.17 points. In the experimental group of animals, beginning from the start of treatment with the gel containing the liquid extract of Xandeliya with pubescent leaves, the inflammatory processes were less pronounced. By the 3rd day, after applying the liquid extract, the inflammation level decreased to 3.17 ± 0.17 points, which was 20.8% lower than the first-day results. In the control group, however, gingival inflammation intensified, with the inflammation level reaching 3.83 ± 0.17 points. By the 5th day, gingival inflammation in the experimental group was statistically significantly 64.3% lower than in the control group. By the 7th day, gingival inflammation in the experimental rats was 201.2% lower compared to the control group.

In the group of rats treated with Kamistad gel, similar results were observed. That is, after applying Kamistad gel, by the 3rd day the inflammation decreased to 3.33 ± 0.33 points, which was 15.0% lower than the first-day results. By the 5th day, gingival inflammation in this group was 91.5% lower than in the control group. By the 7th day, gingival inflammation in the experimental rats was statistically significantly 150.0% lower compared to the control group.

Conclusion. The studied dental gel actively reduces oral inflammation.